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A predictive model for prostate cancer incorporating PSA molecular forms and age

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The diagnostic specificity of prostate specific antigen (PSA) is limited. We aimed to characterize eight anti-PSA monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) to assess the prostate cancer (PCa) diagnostic utility of different PSA molecular forms, total (t) and free (f) PSA and PSA complexed to α_1 -antichymotrypsin (complexed PSA). MAbs were obtained by immunization with PSA and characterized by competition studies, ELISAs and immunoblotting. With them, we developed sensitive and specific ELISAs for these PSA molecular forms and measured them in 301 PCa patients and 764 patients with benign prostate hyperplasia, and analyzed their effectiveness to discriminate both groups using ROC curves. The free-to-total (FPR) and the complexed-to-total PSA (CPR) ratios significantly increased the diagnostic yield of tPSA. Moreover, based on model selection, we constructed a multivariable logistic regression model to predictive PCa that includes tPSA, fPSA, and age as predictors, which reached an optimism-corrected area under the ROC curve (AUC) of 0.86. Our model outperforms the predictive ability of tPSA (AUC 0.71), used in clinical practice. In conclusion, The FPR and CPR showed better diagnostic yield than tPSA. In addition, the PCa predictive model including age, fPSA and complexed PSA, outperformed tPSA detection efficacy. Our model may avoid unnecessary biopsies, preventing harmful side effects and reducing health expenses.

In Europe, prostate cancer (PCa) is the most common solid neoplasm in men, with an incidence rate of 25% of all newly diagnosed cancers and shows the highest death rate after lung and bronchus cancer¹. Men surviving PCa are the largest population of male cancer survivors and comprise approximately 40% of all. Significant controversy concerning PCa overdiagnosis and overtreatment has led to a search for better markers. Overdiagnosis is a minor problem compared to underdiagnosis. Overtreatment is an ethical problem that could be solved when effective tools to differentiate clinically significant from indolent tumours are adopted. Approximately 1.3 million of prostate biopsies are performed every year in the USA. Most of them are negative but 43% will require a new diagnostic biopsy in 3 years². This situation involves side effects and unnecessary expenses.

Prostate specific antigen (PSA), also known as human glandular kallikrein 3, is a member of the kallikrein family which also includes tissue kallikrein and human glandular kallikrein 2 (hK2). PSA is secreted by prostate epithelial cells³ and is present in serum from patients with prostate disease⁴. High levels of PSA are a useful marker for PCa detection⁴, for monitoring follow-up and progression after radical prostatectomy⁵, and for monitoring local or systemic therapy^{6,7}. However, levels of PSA are also increased in some patients with benign prostatic hyperplasia, acute prostatitis⁸ or prostate manipulations, leading to unnecessary negative biopsies or to over detection of non-significant cancers. Nonetheless, PSA screening has saved the lives of many men around the world, is an independent variable for PCa, and is a better predictor of cancer than digital rectal examination (DRE) or transrectal ultrasound diagnosis⁹. So, the suggestions to abandon PSA screening are unjustified. Instead, we should refine the diagnosis with better screening and better biopsy performing.

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Different new biomarkers, cancer metabolism markers or microRNAs are being investigated to improve diagnosis of PCa in different types of samples, such as serum, urine, semen or cell cultures^{10–13}. In addition, different strategies using several PSA molecular forms or ratios, PSA density or velocity¹⁴, proPSA forms, PSA glycoforms¹⁵ or PSA in combination with platelet volume and distribution¹⁶ have been developed in order to improve the specificity of PSA as a biomarker. Moreover, novel score tests to provide the risk of PCa derived from a mathematical algorithm for different kallikrein biomarkers as well as other clinical information, have been developed^{17,18}. They are known as: 4 K Score [total PSA (tPSA), free PSA (fPSA) and intact PSA and human kallikrein 2 hK2]^{19,20}, Prostate Health Index (PHI) (tPSA, fPSA ratio and [−2]proPSA)^{21,22} or Stockholm-3 test^{23,24} (tPSA, fPSA and intact PSA, hK2, MSMB, MIC1, genetic polymorphisms, age, family history, previous prostate biopsy, DRE and prostate volume). Another approach, derived from these scores and estimated in large populations, is the risk calculators (RCs) prediction models, developed to assess patient's individual PCa risk, which show a moderate to well discriminatory ability to predict PCa²⁵. There are other prognostic scores based on genetic approaches, but their results are controversial^{3,26}. In addition, mutations in kallikrein genes are associated with the risk of PCa and tumour aggressiveness^{27,28}.

One of the most promising approaches to improve the specificity of the PSA test to better distinguish between PCa and non-PCa, is the development of assays for measuring different molecular forms of PSA in plasma or serum. PSA is present in circulation in different molecular forms, including fPSA and PSA complexed with α_1 -antichymotrypsin (PSA- α_1 ACT) and with α_2 -macroglobulin (PSA- α_2 M)²⁹, although the most relevant forms are fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT^{30,31}. tPSA, fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT complex levels vary with age, race and ethnicity, body mass index values or the assay kits used³². Nevertheless, these variations are mainly associated with prostate disease. The free-to-total (FPR) and complexed-to-total PSA (CPR) ratios have been shown to provide a better discrimination between PCA and non-PCA^{33,34}. Additionally, hK2 has about 80% homology to PSA and some anti-PSA antibodies may cross-react with this protein. Therefore, the presence of different molecular forms of PSA and hK2 in serum, illustrates the need to develop new anti-PSA antibodies that do not cross-react with hK2 and may distinguish between fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT more precisely.

Here, we report the preparation and characterization of eight anti-PSA monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) and their usefulness in specific sandwich ELISAs for tPSA, fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT complex. We also evaluated the clinical usefulness to discriminate between PCa and non-PCa for these molecular forms, using ROC curves as well as combination of several biomarkers in a predictive model that may enhance sensitivity and specificity of PSA alone. All the assays were performed in citrated plasma samples as we have reported that citrated plasma samples provide higher specificity than serum samples when using FPR and CPR as markers³⁵.

Results

Characterization of monoclonal anti-PSA antibodies. In our study, eight murine anti-PSA mAbs were generated and characterized: M1, M15, M21, M29, M40, M50, M63, and M73. All of them were of the IgG1 with kappa chain type and none exhibited cross-reactivity with female sera, determined by incubation with different relative concentration of antibodies and PSA (see Supplementary Fig. S1), showing that female serum does not contain any component that competes with PSA for antibody binding. The apparent dissociation constant (Kd) of each mAb for immobilized PSA or PSA in solution is shown in Supplementary Table S1, with the M40 mAb showing the highest affinity.

Only two of our eight mAbs showed cross-reactivity with hK2, especially M73, so it could only be used as a secondary antibody (see Supplementary Fig. S2). Four combinations, M1/M21*, M21/M40*, M40/M50* and M40/M73*, detected fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT with the same efficiency (see Supplementary Fig. S3). Hence, we selected the pair M40/M73* to set up an ELISA for tPSA. This assay does not recognize hK2, is equimolar (detects all PSA molecular forms in equal molar ratios), and has a detection limit of 0.1 μ g/L (see Supplementary Figs. S2–S4).

Immunoassays for the PSA molecular forms. All combinations with M63 were specific for fPSA (see Supplementary Fig. S4). We selected the pair M63/M50* to set up an assay specific for fPSA. The assay does not detect complexed PSA, has a detection limit of 0.04 μ g/L (see Supplementary Fig. S4), and gave no signal with hK2 concentrations up to 20 μ g/L.

There were three combinations (M1/M40*, M1/M50* and M1/M73*) that reacted slightly more efficiently with PSA- α_1 ACT than with fPSA (see Supplementary Fig. S4), suggesting that M1 may not be useful to measure PSA- α_1 ACT complex. Therefore, we selected the combination M40/polyclonal anti- α_1 ACT* pair to measure PSA- α_1 ACT in plasma. It gave a good dose-response curve with purified PSA- α_1 ACT diluted both in buffer and in plasma and no signal was obtained either with fPSA up to 2000 μ g/L or with purified α_1 ACT up to 500 mg/L. The assay has a detection limit of 0.05 μ g/L of complexed PSA (see Supplementary Fig. S4), and gave no signal with hK2 concentrations up to 20 μ g/L.

Clinical usefulness of the PSA molecular forms. We studied 764 patients with benign biopsy (BB) and 301 patients with PCa. Table 1 shows median with the first and third quartiles in brackets, or n with % in parenthesis for tPSA, fPSA, PSA- α_1 ACT, PSA- α_2 M, PSA-hk2, as well as FPR, CPR and FPR/CPR ratio, as markers to discriminate between PCa and BB. The concentration of tPSA, fPSA, PSA- α_1 ACT, PSA- α_2 M, PSA-hk2 and CPR was significantly higher in patients with PCa than in those with BB ($P < 0.001$, $P = 0.012$, $P < 0.001$, $P < 0.001$ and $P < 0.001$, respectively), whereas prostate volume, FPR and FPR/CPR ratio were significantly higher in BB than in PCa ($P < 0.001$) (Table 1). Using tPSA levels, we also estimated the PSA density (tPSA/prostate volume) for all patients, which was significantly higher in PCa patients than in BB ($P < 0.001$).

	PCa (n = 301)	BB (n = 764)	P-value
Age, years	67 [64–73]	66 [61–70]	<0.001
Prostate volume, cm ³	34 [26–48]	44 [31–57]	<0.001
PSA density, µg/L*cm ³	0.23 [0.13–0.45]	0.15 [0.09–0.25]	<0.001
tPSA <4 µg/L	27 (9%)	136 (18%)	<0.001
tPSA ≥4 µg/L	174 (91%)	628 (82%)	
DRE normal	102 (34%)	581 (76%)	<0.001
DRE abnormal	199 (66%)	183 (24%)	
tPSA, µg/L	9.9 [6.2–23.7]	6.5 [4.5–9.4]	<0.001
fPSA, µg/L	1.8 [0.7–4.0]	1.4 [0.8–2.4]	0.012
PSA-α ₁ ACT, µg/L	9.1 [5.5–17.4]	4.8 [3.2–6.9]	<0.001
PSA-α ₂ M, µg/L	1.9 [0.5–4.4]	1.0 [0.4–1.7]	<0.001
hK2-α ₂ M, µg/L	5.2 (2.7–13.6)	3.1 (1.9–5.2)	<0.001
fPSA ratio (FPR)	14 [10–18]	23 [16–32]	<0.001
Complex PSA ratio (CPR)	89 [78–96]	75 [62–86]	<0.001
FPR/CPR ratio	0.16 [0.11–0.23]	0.31 [0.19–0.51]	<0.001
Patients with			
1 biopsy	85 (28%)	384 (50%)	
2 biopsies	134 (45%)	223 (29%)	
3 biopsies	69 (23%)	137 (18%)	
4 biopsies	13 (4%)	20 (3%)	
n (%)			
Patients, n (%):			
- with Gleason score	164 (54.5%)		
- without Gleason score	137 (45.5%)		
*Gleason score 6, n (%)	103 (63%)		
Gleason score ≥7, n (%)	61 (37%)		

Table 1. Clinical characteristics of the cohort of PCa and BB patients studied. Data are presented as median with the first and third quartiles in brackets, or n with % in parenthesis. *Gleason score was also available in 164 PCa patients.

We used two types of analyses to assess the clinical performance of the parameters studied, one through ROC curves grouping patients into subgroups according to their tPSA level, and the other through multivariable logistic regression models with continuous variables, for generalizable results.

Table 2 shows the sensitivity, specificity, and AUC values for the group of patients with tPSA between ≥4 and <10 µg/L. For this subgroup of patients, FPR (AUC = 0.81), CPR (AUC = 0.79) and FPR/CPR ratio (AUC = 0.79) gave a better discrimination than tPSA (AUC = 0.56).

Supplementary Tables S4–S7 show the sensitivity, specificity, and AUC values for the different subgroups analysed: whole cohort of patients, patients with tPSA between ≥2.5 and ≤4 µg/L, patients with tPSA between ≥4 and <10 µg/L and patients with tPSA between 10 and <20 µg/L. For the whole cohort of analysed patients, the FPR/CPR ratio (0.82) and FPR (0.78) gave a better discrimination than tPSA (0.69) (Supplementary Table S4). For the group of patients with tPSA between ≥2.5 and <4 ng/ml, the FPR/CPR ratio (0.77) and FPR (0.76) again gave better discrimination than tPSA (0.53) (Supplementary Table S5). For the tPSA range between ≥10 and <20 µg/L, FPR (0.80) and CPR (0.79) gave the best discrimination compared to tPSA (0.55) (Supplementary Table S7). In this range, using a cut-off point of 4.4 for the FPR/CPR ratio we would have avoided 30% biopsies without losing any PCa patient.

Clinical variables, age, PSA density, tPSA, fPSA, PSA-α₁ACT, PSA-α₂M, FPR, CPR and FPR/CPR were also analyzed in multivariable logistic regression models. Table 3 shows the different models used for discriminating between PCa and BB using the akaike information criterion (AIC). The best model, according to the AIC criterion, included only the variables: age (OR = 1.75, 95% CI: 1.31–3.36 (per 10 years), $P < 0.001$), tPSA and fPSA values (OR = 22.55, 95% CI: 13.1–40.5, $P < 0.001$; and OR = 0.05, 95% CI: 0.025–0.095, $P < 0.001$, respectively), as well as their interaction (OR = 1.31, 95% CI: 1.08–1.6, $P = 0.007$) (Table 4). Due to their skewed distribution, tPSA, fPSA and their interaction were log-transformed prior to modelling. With a likelihood ratio test we compared the performance of our elected model and the other models proposed. As depicted in Table 3, our model outperformed all others. Our model substantially improves the predictive capacity of PCa compared to that of tPSA. It achieved an apparent AUC of 0.86 (95% CI: 0.83–0.89) and an optimism-corrected AUC of 0.86, compared to AUC of 0.71 (95% CI: 0.67–0.75) for tPSA (Fig. 1). The formula for predicting the probability (Pr) of PCa would be:

$$\Pr(PCa) = \frac{e^{-10.57 + 0.056 * Age + 3.116 * \log(tPSA) - 2.995 * \log(fPSA) + 0.268 * \log(tPSA) * \log(fPSA)}}{1 + e^{-10.57 + 0.056 * Age + 3.116 * \log(tPSA) - 2.995 * \log(fPSA) + 0.268 * \log(tPSA) * \log(fPSA)}}$$

Assay	Cut-off value	Sensitivity	Specificity	AUC (95% CI)
Total PSA, µg/L	>4.04	100	1	0.56 (0.53–0.61) ^b
	>4.20	95	6	
	>4.60	90	14	
	>4.90	85	21	
PSA density	≤0.78	100	2	0.52 (0.43–0.61)
	≤0.55	95	5	
	≤0.49	90	8	
	≤0.41	85	14	
Free PSA, µg/L	≤3.43	100	3	0.73 (0.68–0.76)
	≤2.01	95	25	
	≤1.52	90	45	
	≤1.42	85	49	
PSA-α ₁ ACT, µg/L	>2.25	100	2	0.71 (0.67–0.74)
	>3.36	95	18	
	>3.96	90	34	
	>4.05	85	36	
FPR	≤53	100	1	0.81 (0.78–0.84)
	≤27	95	37	
	≤23	90	46	
	≤19	85	61	
CPR	>44	100	3	0.79 (0.75–0.82)
	>69	95	35	
	>72	90	43	
	>79	85	60	
FPR/CPR	≤23	100	1	0.79 (0.76–0.82)
	≤6	95	35	
	≤5	90	50	
	≤4	85	55	

Table 2. Sensitivity (%), specificity (%), and AUC for total PSA, free PSA, PSA density, PSA-α₁ACT, free-to-total PSA ratio (FPR), complexed-to-total PSA ratio (CPR) and FPR/CPR ratio for the 126 patients with PCa and 464 with BB with tPSA between ≥4 and <10 µg/L. ^aCI, confidence interval; ^b*P* < 0.001 for the difference in AUC for total PSA vs all other parameters. *P* > 0.05 for all other comparisons.

Model	AIC	LR-test <i>P</i> -value 1 st vs. others
Age + log(tPSA) + log(fPSA) + log(tPSA)*log(fPSA)	629.61	—
Age + log(tPSA) + log(fPSA)	635.88	0.004
Age + CPR + FPR	704.86	<0.001
Age + log(PSA-α ₁ ACT) + log(fPSA) + log(tPSA) + log(PSA-α ₂ M)	637.12	<0.001
Age + log(PSA-α ₁ ACT) + log(fPSA) + log(tPSA) + CPR + FPR + log(PSA-α ₂ M)	631.34	0.91

Table 3. Different models used for discriminating between PCa and BB patients using the AIC. The model with the lower AIC value was selected as the best model. *Indicates an interaction relationship.

	OR	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	<i>P</i> -value
Age	1.058	1.027	1.09	<0.001
log(tPSA)	22.554	13.122	40.451	<0.001
log(fPSA)	0.05	0.025	0.095	<0.001
log(tPSA)*log(fPSA)	1.308	1.084	1.6	0.007

Table 4. Multivariable logistic regression models constructed to analyze the probability of PCa occurrence using clinical variables and different combinations of PSA molecular forms. Only those variables that estimate the best akaike information criterion (AIC) were shown. *Indicates an interaction relationship.

In order to assess whether our selected model was really better than by biopsy all, we performed a decision curve analysis comparing our selected model to total PSA and biopsy all (Supplementary Fig. S5). The results show that our model improves the standardized net benefit over all the range of thresholds compared to biopsy

Figure 1. ROC curves for the predictive model (age, tPSA, fPSA and tPSA*fPSA) compared to that obtained for tPSA using mAbs. The area under the curve (AUC) and interquartile range in parenthesis are shown.

all and over most of the threshold values compared to total PSA values. Thus, standardized net benefit values are higher in our model compared to biopsy all starting at a probability of 4%. This difference is statistically significant starting at a probability of 13%.

In order to ease the interpretation of the results of the model, we represented its sensitivity and specificity profile plot (Supplementary Fig. S6). Using this profile plot we may select a sensitivity (for example 90%), obtaining a specificity of 58%.

We also generated an effect plot depicting the relationship between tPSA, fPSA and the probability of cancer (Supplementary Fig. S7). It shows that increasing levels of tPSA are associated with higher probabilities of cancer, and increasing levels of fPSA are associated with lower probabilities of cancer. The effect of one biomarker can mask the effect of the other at extreme values (i.e., low values of tPSA always result in low probabilities of cancer no matter what the fPSA values are, and high values of fPSA always result in low probabilities of cancer no matter how high the tPSA values are). We also provided as supplementary material a spreadsheet (see supplementary Dataset) for performing straightforward predictions. For example, for an 80 years old patient, if tPSA is 9 ng/mL and fPSA is 1.5 ng/mL, the calculated risk of PCa is 44.5% (see supplementary Dataset).

Furthermore, we estimated the improvement of our new predictive model versus the classical markers (tPSA levels) using the net reclassification improvement (NRI) and the integrated discrimination improvement (IDI). We observed that our predictive model had an NRI value of 0.870, splitted as NRI for the event (PCa) of 0.374 and NRI for the non-event (BB) of 0.496 (Supplementary Table S7). The IDI value was 0.201. So, the NRI and IDI scores indicate that our combination of several biomarkers in a predictive model may enhance sensitivities [increase for PCa (sensitivity) = 0.142] and specificities [decrease for BB (specificity) = 0.0587] of PSA alone, improving the ability to estimate the risk of PCa.

Additionally, we have analyzed the correlation between the Gleason score and the risk of PCa, calculated with our predictive model. For these analyses involving the Gleason score we only included samples from patients with reliable Gleason scores. In many cases, we couldn't find the data, or the grading was not reliable because of the sample specimen analyzed. In the 164 PCa patients for whom we had the Gleason score, the coefficient of correlation was $r = 0.56$ (95% CI: 0.45–0.66, $P < 0.0001$) and the number of patients with tumours with Gleason scores ≥ 7 increased as the PCa risk increased (Fig. 2). Moreover, the AUC estimated by introducing the PCa risk, calculated with our model, and the dichotomized Gleason score (< 7 and ≥ 7), was 0.83 (95% CI: 0.77–0.89, $P < 0.0001$). Using a cut-off value of PCa risk $> 50\%$, the specificity was 39% for a sensitivity of 95%. This means that, using a sensitivity of 95%, we could have avoided about 39% of biopsies to PCa patients with a Gleason score < 7 .

Discussion

Over the past decade, PSA has been shown to be the most valuable diagnostic and prognostic marker in oncology. However, its reliability as screening tool for PCa remains controversial due to its lack of specificity. Several non-malignant conditions of the prostate, such as BB, are associated with an increased PSA levels³⁵. Alternative biomarkers for PCa have emerged with the aim of increasing the diagnostic specificity, prognosis and staging of this cancer^{3,14,36–41}. Some of these new diagnostic tools are related to PSA, such as PHI^{21,40}, 4 K Score^{19,20} and the

Figure 2. Percentage of PCa patients with Gleason score ≥ 7 in relation to PCa risk.

STHLM3 test^{23,24}, or RCs to assess the PCa risk of a patient²⁵. However, their clinical applicability is controversial and remain a matter of personal choice whether to use it in daily clinical practice.

PSA circulates in two forms, fPSA (30%) or PSA complexed to α_1 ACT (70%). The FPR or the CPR have become important markers to improve the specificity of tPSA and the differential diagnosis of BB and PCa^{33,42–45}. There are different immunoassays for detection of these PSA molecular forms with different assay manufacturers. In systematic review, Roddam *et al.*³⁴ described the diagnostic ability of the FPR and CPR in men with tPSA levels between 2 and 10 ng/mL, and its impact on clinical practice. They concluded that their use in this segment of patients could reduce the number of unnecessary biopsies whilst maintaining a high cancer detection rate.

Accordingly, we proposed the use of specific homemade ELISAs for tPSA, fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT complex by using different pairs of antibodies that do not recognize hK2. These assays are equimolar and show detection limits and variation coefficients that are in all cases adequate, and have been validated in a large cohort of patients with PCa and BB (more information is shown in Supplementary material).

Our results show that PSA- α_1 ACT, FPR, CPR and FPR/CPR ratio significantly increase the diagnostic yield of tPSA when patients are classified according to different tPSA ranges (see Supplementary Tables S4–S6). In the diagnostic gray zone of 4 to 10 μ g/l tPSA, using a cut-off value of 27 for FPR, 69 for CPR or 6 for FPR/CPR ratio (95% specificity), we could avoid about 35% of biopsies compared to 6% of biopsies avoided when using a cut-off value of 4.2 μ g/l tPSA.

Our results compare well with those obtained with the PHI and [–2]proPSA markers, showing similar or better clinical performance for PCa detection⁴⁶. There, the PHI was significantly higher in PCa patients than in patients without PCa, with an AUC of 0.70. Our results show AUCs for FPR, CPR and FPR/CPR, ranging from 0.79 to 0.81.

In order to improve the discrimination between PCa and BB, we compared our new predictive model to the classical marker (tPSA levels) using the NRI and the IDI. Our results, compared to those obtained with the PHI, with an AUC ranging from 0.70 to 0.77^{45,46}, showed that our predictive model including age, tPSA, fPSA and the interaction of tPSA and fPSA, rendered a superior AUC (0.85; 95% CI = 0.83–0.89), demonstrating a better clinical performance for PCa detection. Additionally, our model shows another advantage, the independence from prostate volume. Only age is required as a valuable clinical factor, combined with the PSA molecular forms. Similar results are found when comparing our predictive model with the results described for the 4K Score panel²⁰, which could distinguish PCa and BB with good accuracy, with an AUC from 0.81 to 0.84, respectively, similar to that estimated with our predictive model (0.85). When we compared our predictive model with the seven well known RCs, that shown an AUC range between 0.64 and 0.72, we observed again how our predictive model exhibits a better discriminatory ability to predict PCa. And if we select only patients with clinically significant PCa, the RCs study with the highest AUC is 0.77, lower than the AUC obtained in our predictive model for all patients²⁵.

Finally, Vickers *et al.*¹⁹, described a predictive model similar to ours, based on how additional kallikreins (fPSA, intact PSA, and hK2) could enhance discrimination of PCa diagnosis compared to a classical laboratory model (including age and tPSA) or a classical clinical model (including age, tPSA and DRE). They described a homemade ELISA to identify intact PSA and hK2 kallikreins, based on modified mAbs with less nonspecific assay interference. This study obtained an AUC of 0.64 for tPSA levels, 0.70 including DRE, and 0.76 including age and additional kallikreins. We propose an alternative mAb design to quantify other markers (fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT), based on equimolar tests that show no unspecific interactions with others kallikreins. Our strategy has allowed us to develop a predictive model with highest AUC, simple and easy to introduce in daily clinical practice.

Although our study had as main objective to identify a predictive model of PCa, given the current interest in identifying patients with more aggressive tumours, we decided to also analyze whether the predictive model of PCa obtained was also able to discriminate between aggressive and indolent phenotypes of PCa, for which we included in the study the 164 PCa patients for whom we had a reliable Gleason score. We observed a significant correlation between the Gleason score and PCa risk obtained with our model. Furthermore, the number of patients with a score ≥ 7 increased with the increase in the risk of PCa (Fig. 2), and the risk of PCa was significantly higher in patients with Gleason score ≥ 7 tumours (70%) compared with Gleason score 6 tumours (39%) ($P < 0.0001$). A similar result was reported by Stephan *et al.*⁴⁵ using the PHI index. From the AUC performed introducing the PCa risk, calculated with our model, and the dichotomized Gleason score (< 7 and ≥ 7), using a cut-off point of PCa risk $> 50\%$, the specificity was 39% for a sensitivity of 95%, indicating that with our model we could have avoided about 39% of biopsies to PCa patients with a Gleason score < 7 .

A limitation of this study is that our predictive model needs to be validated in a prospective study before prostate biopsy has been conducted, and needs an external validation using a multicenter study population. However, prospective population-based screening strategies are difficult to implement in daily clinical practice and require approval by local authorities. Another limitation is the unfeasibility to gather the variables needed for the estimation of proPSA and 4K-panel, so no head-to-head comparison of the different methods could be made. Finally, of the 301 patients with PCa we only had 164 patients with the available Gleason score. It would be necessary to confirm our results with a higher number of PCa patients.

In conclusion, we have developed and validated specific and sensitive immunoassays to quantify different PSA molecular forms. Our results using ROC curves for different tPSA ranges show that the FPR and CPR significantly increase the discriminating power of tPSA, fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT.

In addition, the combination of tPSA, fPSA and age in a predictive model, increases the diagnostic power of tPSA, widely used in clinical practice, and may identify patients with a more aggressive tumours. Thus, the use of our predictive model may avoid unnecessary biopsies while high sensitivity is maintained, thus reducing unnecessary side effects in hundreds of thousands of patients every year and consequently unnecessary health expenses. A diagnosis in time and in early stages is very advisable and valuable, since it represents the critical stage regarding treatment and survival of the patient.

Material and Methods

Study subjects. This case-finding study included 1,065 patients with at least one prostate biopsy, 764 with BB and 301 with PCa, selected for having a positive DRE and/or a tPSA $\geq 4 \mu\text{g/L}$. Samples were collected between 1997 and 2001.

PCa was objectively diagnosed by transrectal ultrasound-guided prostate biopsy, or by examination of tissue specimens following transurethral prostatectomy (incidental diagnosis). According to clinical situation, only 17 of the 301 PCa patients studied (5.7%) underwent transurethral resection for prostatic obstruction, a small percentage that would not cause deviation in the study population.

A diagnosis of BB was considered when patients had a negative biopsy and also when patients had an increase in prostate volume ($> 40 \text{ cm}^3$) along with the following symptoms: obstructive symptoms, hesitant or intermittent micturition, decreased strength and thinning of the urinary stream gauge.

All participants were enrolled after giving written informed consent according to protocols approved by the ethics review board at La Fe University Hospital (reference no. 3009/0085). The procedures followed were in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975 as revised in 2008.

Blood collection. Blood was collected into Vacuette® sodium citrate tubes, centrifuged at $1,800 \times g$ for 30 minutes at 4°C and plasma samples were aliquoted and frozen at -70°C until analysis.

Reagents. Purified hK2 and a monoclonal anti-hK2 antibody (HK1G86.1) that does not cross-react with PSA were provided by Hybritech Inc. (San Diego, CA). Biotin-NHS, human α_1 ACT and α_2 M, and rabbit anti-human α_2 M (IgG fraction) were obtained from Calbiochem (La Jolla, CA). Rabbit anti-human α_1 ACT (IgG fraction) was purchased from Dako A/S (Glostrup, Denmark). Aprotinin-Sepharose, casein, bovine serum albumin, horseradish peroxidase (HRP, type VI, RZ = 3.2), anti-mouse IgG (goat)-HRP, anti-mouse IgG (rabbit)-HRP whole molecule, Tween 20, hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), O-phenylenediamine (OPD), benzamidine chloride, dimethyl sulfoxide and dithiothreitol were from Sigma Chem. Co. (St. Louis, MO). Glutaraldehyde and 1,10-phenanthroline chloride were from E. Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Streptavidin-HRP (SAHRP), biotinylated horse polyclonal anti-mouse IgG antibody and NBT/BCIP were from Pierce (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA USA). Streptavidin-alkaline phosphatase was from Bio-Rad. CM-Sephadex, Sephacryl S-200 and CNBr-activated Sepharose 4B were obtained from Pharmacia (Uppsala, Sweden).

Production and characterization of monoclonal anti-PSA antibodies. See supplementary results for the production, purification, isotyping, calculation of the apparent Kd (Supplementary Table S1),

biotinylation, serum competition (Supplementary Fig. S1), SDS-PAGE and Western blots, reactivity of anti-PSA mAbs on immunoblots towards fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT complex (Supplementary Table S2), competition between unlabelled and labelled mAbs for binding to PSA (Supplementary Table S3), cross-reactivity with hK2 (Supplementary Fig. S2) and reactivity of several pairs of anti-PSA mAbs towards fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT complex (Supplementary Fig. S3).

Immunoassay for total PSA. The assay for tPSA was performed with M40 as capturing antibody and biotinylated (*) M73 as detecting antibody. Plates were coated with 5 mg/L of M40. After washing and blocking with blocking buffer, 50 μ L/well of duplicated samples or calibrators were added and incubated for 1 h at room temperature (RT). After washing, 50 μ L/well of M73* at a dilution of 1/8000 in 0.01 mol/L Tris-HCl, pH 7.4, 0.14 mol/L NaCl, 0.5 g Thimerosal per liter, 0.5 mL Tween 20 per liter, was added and incubated for 1 h at RT. After washing, SAHRP at 1/4000 was applied as described above. Colour was developed with OPD substrate and the reaction was stopped after 5 min with 35 μ L/well of 4 mol/L H₂SO₄.

Immunoassay for PSA - α_1 ACT complex. The assay for PSA- α_1 ACT was performed with M40 as capturing antibody and a polyclonal HRP-labelled anti- α_1 ACT antibody as detecting antibody. Plates were coated with 5 mg/L of M40. After washing and blocking, 50 μ L/well of duplicated samples or calibrators were added and incubated for 1 h at RT. After washing, 50 μ L/well of HRP-labelled anti- α_1 ACT antibody at a dilution of 1/2000 was added and incubated for 1 h at RT. After washing, colour was developed with OPD substrate and the reaction was stopped after 5 min with 35 μ L/well of 4 mol/L H₂SO₄.

Immunoassay for fPSA. The assay for fPSA was performed with M63 as capturing antibody and M50* as detecting antibody. Plates were coated with 5 mg/L of M63. After washing and blocking, 50 μ L/well of duplicated samples or calibrators were added and incubated for 1 h at RT. After washing, 50 μ L/well of M50* at a dilution of 1/10000 was added and incubated for 1 h at RT. After washing, SAHRP at 1/4000 was applied as described above. Colour was developed with OPD substrate and the reaction was stopped after 5 min with 35 μ L/well of 4 mol/L H₂SO₄.

Immunoassay for PSA - α_2 M complex. The assay for PSA- α_2 M complex was performed as reported before for the activated protein C- α_2 M complex⁴⁷. Briefly, plasma samples were pre-treated with dithiothreitol and then with iodoacetamide, in order to expose PSA epitopes. The M40 anti-PSA antibody was used as coating antibody and biotinylated anti-IgG antibody was used as detecting antibody. The detection range of the PSA- α_2 M assay was 0.1 to 4.0 ng/ml of complex.

Statistical analysis. Data were summarized using median, standard deviation and 1st and 3rd quartile in the case of continuous variables and relative and absolute frequencies in the case of categorical variables. Multivariable logistic regression models were constructed with different combinations of the PSA molecular forms and clinical variables. Selection of the best model for discriminating between PCa and BB was performed using the AIC⁴⁸. Calibration of the final model was assessed using a scatter plot of the predicted versus observed probabilities using 500 bootstrap replicates of the sample. Although the bootstrap is not a substitute of a large sample external validation, it is the best method for assessing calibration when no external validation is feasible. The predictive ability of the model was assessed by estimating an optimism-corrected area under the curve (AUC) for the receiver operator characteristic (ROC) analysis, and using 1000 bootstrap replicates. All these statistical analyses were performed using R (version 3.4.2) and R-packages pROC (1.10.0) and rms (5.1-1). Moreover, the improvement of the new (multivariable logistic regression model) versus the classical marker, tPSA, were estimated by using the NRI and the IDI. For that, the R-package Hmisc (4.1-1) was used for the NRI and IDI of logistic regression models⁴⁹. NRI and IDI values were provided as a complement of the AUC values for the different models, following specific guidelines⁴⁹, and providing only 95% CI for NRI and IDI. The AUC to assess the diagnostic accuracy of each parameter was calculated using a commercially available computer program for medical statistics⁵⁰. Analysis of ROC curves using clinical groups was performed on patients according to tPSA levels: a) tPSA between 0.76 and 975 μ g/L (whole cohort), b) ≥ 2.5 and < 4.0 μ g/L, c) ≥ 4 and < 10 μ g/L and d) ≥ 10 and < 20 μ g/L. Using the same statistical program, we estimated the AUC introducing the PCa risk, calculated with our model, and the dichotomized Gleason score (< 7 and ≥ 7).

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Author contributions

A.F.P., M.R., L.M. and J.O. performed the experiments, analyzed the data and revised the manuscript. M.M. and C.D.V.-D. recruited patients and revised the manuscript. D.H. performed the statistical analysis. M.J.H. participated in the study concept and design, analyzed the data and revised the manuscript. F.E., P.M. and S.N. performed the research, participated in the study concept and design, analyzed the data, wrote and revised the manuscript. All the authors have accepted responsibility for the entire content of this submitted manuscript and approved submission.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

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Supporting Information

A predictive model for prostate cancer incorporating PSA molecular forms and age

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Supplementary Material & Methods

Purification of PSA

PSA was purified from seminal fluid as described by Sensabaugh and Blake¹ with the following modifications: each semen donation was collected into 4 mL of a solution containing 200 mmol/L benzamidine-HCl and 20 mmol/L phenanthroline-HCl in distilled water, to reduce PSA inactivation. Semen was immediately centrifuged at 10,000g for 5 min at 4 °C and the supernatant was stored at -80 °C. Samples from 14 donors were thawed at 37 °C for 5 min, mixed with 2 volumes of 0.01 mol/L potassium phosphate buffer, pH 6.9, containing 30 mmol/L benzamidine-HCl and 10 mmol/L phenanthroline-HCl, and dialyzed against 20 volumes of the same buffer. The dialyzed material was centrifuged at 5,000g for 15 min and applied to a CM-Sephadex column and then to a Sephacryl S-200 column. Fractions containing PSA from the last column were concentrated and dialyzed on a PM-10 Amicon membrane against 0.025 mol/L Tris-HCl, pH 7.4, 0.5 mol/L NaCl, 0.2g Na-azide per liter, and applied to an aprotinin-Sepharose column as previously described². The final preparation had a concentration of 2.5 g/L as determined by absorption at 280 nm, using an extinction coefficient $\epsilon^{0.1\%}$ of 1.84. A concentration of 2.70 and 2.53 g/L was calculated using the Hybritech Tandem-E assay and a homemade PSA assay,³ respectively.

Preparation of polyclonal anti-PSA antibodies

Specific rabbit anti-human PSA antibody and anti-PSA IgG labelled with HRP were obtained following standard procedures as previously reported.⁴

Preparation of PSA- α_1 ACT complex

The complex was partially purified from plasma of a patient with 86% of the PSA complexed to α_1 ACT using a reported method⁵ with slight modifications. The plasma was filtered on a 2.6x90 cm Sephacryl S-200 column equilibrated in 0.1 mol/L potassium phosphate buffer pH 6.9, 0.5 mol/L NaCl, 0.2g Na-azide per liter, at 14 mL/h, collecting fractions of 1 mL. The degree of

separation between PSA and PSA- α_1 ACT complex was analyzed by specific ELISAs for total PSA (tPSA) and PSA- α_1 ACT complex. The filtration effectively separated most of the free PSA (fPSA) (30 kDa) from PSA- α_1 ACT complex (90 kDa). No efforts were made to separate free α_1 ACT from PSA- α_1 ACT complex, since it is known that an excess of inhibitor stabilizes the complex. Fractions containing PSA- α_1 ACT were pooled and concentrated on a PM-10 Amicon membrane. The final preparation contained a tPSA concentration of 206.6 $\mu\text{g/L}$, and a concentration of PSA complexed with α_1 ACT of 191.3 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (7% of the tPSA was in the fPSA form).

Production and purification of monoclonal antibodies

Hybridomas secreting anti-PSA monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) were obtained by immunization of BALB/c mice with 60 μg PSA purified from human seminal plasma by standard procedures as previously described.⁶ Hybridomas were screened in ELISA plate wells containing immobilized PSA. To this end, plates were coated at 4 °C overnight with 50 μL PSA (3 mg/L) in 0.1 mol/L sodium carbonate buffer, pH 9.6. After washing and blocking with 0.01 mol/L Tris-HCl, 0.14 mol/L NaCl, pH 7.4 (TBS) buffer containing 10 g casein per liter, 0.2 ml Tween 20 per liter and 0.4 g sodium azide per liter (blocking buffer), undiluted supernatants were incubated with immobilized PSA for 2 h at room temperature (RT). mAbs were detected with an anti-mouse IgG (goat)-HRP. mAbs were purified from mouse ascites fluid using a column of PSA coupled to CNBr-activated Sepharose 4B according to the manufacturer's specifications.

Antibody isotyping

Isotypes of mAbs were determined using the Mouse Typer Sub-Isotyping Kit from Bio-Rad.

Determination of the apparent dissociation constants

The apparent dissociation constants (Kd) were calculated by direct ELISA. Wells were coated

with 100 g/L of purified PSA overnight at 4 °C. Then, several concentrations of mAbs (ranging from 0.003 nmol/L to 600 nmol/L) in blocking buffer were incubated with immobilized PSA for 1 h at RT. The mAb bound was detected with anti-mouse IgG (rabbit)-HRP whole molecule. Furthermore, we evaluated the affinity of each mAb for PSA in solution. Plates were coated overnight at 4 °C with mAbs at 5 mg/L. After washing and blocking, PSA was added at different concentrations (ranging from 0.098 to 400 µg/L) in blocking buffer and plates were incubated for 1 h at RT. Bound PSA was detected with a polyclonal HRP-labelled anti-PSA antibody.

The Kd was calculated from the concentration of mAb (or purified PSA) that gave an absorbance equal to 50% of the absorbance obtained with a saturated concentration of antibody (or PSA).

Biotinylation of antibodies

mAbs and anti-IgG antibody were labelled with biotin-NHS-ester, according to the manufacturer's specifications. Briefly, 1 mL (2 g/L) of each antibody was incubated for 2 h at room temperature with 0.2 mL (1.5 g/L) of biotin-NHS dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide. After dialysis, immunoreactivity of biotinylated mAbs were assessed by ELISA with PSA immobilized directly on plates. Plates were coated with 50 µL/well of 100 µg/L PSA in 0.1 mol/L sodium carbonate buffer, pH 9.6, at 4 °C overnight. After blocking and washing, the native and biotinylated mAbs were incubated with immobilized PSA at different concentrations in blocking buffer (ranged from 0.025 to 6 mg/L). After washing with 0.01 mol/L Tris-HCl, pH 7.4, 0.14 mol/L NaCl, 0.5 g Thimerosal per liter, 0.5 mL Tween 20 per liter (conjugated buffer), plates were incubated with 50 µL/well of anti-mouse IgG (rabbit)-HRP whole molecule at a 1/1000 dilution. Colour was developed with the OPD substrate during 8 min and the reaction was stopped with 4 mol/L H₂SO₄.

Serum competition

Serum from women was diluted 1/2 with 0.01 mol/L sodium phosphate, 0.137 mol/L NaCl, 2.7 mmol/L KCl, pH 7.4 and 50 μ L/well was added to ELISA plates, previously coated with 50 μ L/well of 0.5 or 5.0 mg/L anti-PSA mAbs. After blocking and washing, 50 μ L of 180 μ g/L PSA (wells with 0.5 mg/L mAb) or either 90 μ g/L or 500 μ g/L PSA (wells with 5 mg/L mAb) was added and incubated for 2 h at RT. Bound PSA was detected with a polyclonal HRP-labelled anti-PSA antibody at a concentration of 6 ng/L. Finally, colour was developed by adding 50 μ L of a solution of 400 mg/L OPD in 0.1 mol/L Na citrate, 0.2 mol/L Na phosphate, pH 5.0, containing 400 μ L of 30% H₂O₂ per liter. The reaction was stopped after 5 min by adding 35 μ L/well of 4 mol/L H₂SO₄. The absorbance of the colour formed was read in an ELISA microplate autoreader at 492 nm.

SDS-PAGE and Western blots

SDS-PAGE was performed as reported by Laemmli et al⁷. PSA or PSA- α_1 ACT was denatured under non-reducing or reducing (10 mmol/L dithiothreitol) conditions. After electrophoresis on 10% SDS-polyacrylamide gels, proteins were transferred to nitrocellulose membranes. The membranes were blocked with 5% non-fat milk in TBS buffer for 2 h at RT. mAbs were diluted to their optimal concentrations in 1% non-fat milk in TBS buffer and incubated with membranes 2 h at RT. Membranes were washed 3 times for 10 min and incubated with biotinylated-anti mouse IgG at 0.75 mg/L for 40 min. Thereafter, membranes were washed 3 times for 10 min and incubated with streptavidin-alkaline phosphatase for 20 min at RT. After washing, colour was developed with NBT/BCIP.

Sandwich ELISA assays

The eight mAbs were tested in all possible combinations in a sandwich format, excepting M15 because of its low affinity. Plates were coated overnight at 4 °C with 50 μ L/well of 5 mg/L mAb. After washing and blocking, PSA or PSA complexed to α_1 ACT was added at different

concentrations (ranging from 15 µg/L to 0.029 µg/L) in blocking buffer and plates were incubated for 1 h at RT. Thereafter, plates were incubated for 1 h at RT with 50 µl/well of 2 mg/L biotinylated anti-PSA mAb in 0.01 mol/L Tris-HCl, pH 7.4, 0.14 mol/L NaCl, 0.5 g thimerosal per liter, 0.5 mL Tween 20 per liter. After washing, plates were incubated for 20 min at RT with 50 µL/well of SAHRP diluted at 1/5000 in 0.01 mol/L Tris-HCl, pH 7.4, 0.14 mol/L NaCl, 0.5 g Thimerosal per liter, 0.5 mL Tween 20 per liter. After washing, colour was developed by adding 50 µL/well of a solution of 400 mg/L OPD in 0.12 mol/L Na citrate, 0.2 mol/L Na phosphate, pH 5.0, containing 400 µL of 30% H₂O₂ per liter. The reaction was stopped by adding 35 µL/well of 4 mol/L H₂SO₄. The absorbance of the colour formed was read in an ELISA microplate autoreader at 492 nm.

Cross-reactivity with hK2

To elucidate whether the anti-PSA mAbs recognized hK2 we performed sandwich ELISAs. Plates were coated overnight at 4 °C with 50 µl of 5 mg/L mAb. After washing and blocking, 50 µL of hK2 at 20 mg/L or PSA at 20 µg/L were added and incubated for 1 h at RT. For comparison, a specific anti-hK2 mAb was also analyzed. HK2 or PSA bound were detected with the polyclonal anti-PSA labelled with HRP.

Competitive binding to immobilized PSA

Additional investigation into epitope recognition by the eight mAbs was facilitated by competitive binding to immobilized PSA. PSA antigen was immobilized on microtiter wells, and the ability of any antibody to block the binding of another was evaluated. The ability to block binding would indicate identical or overlapping epitope specificity. Plates were coated with 50 µL/well of 100 mg/L fPSA. After blocking and washing, the plates were incubated for 1 h with one of the mAbs at 50 mg/L in blocking buffer or only with blocking buffer. Serial dilutions of the biotinylated forms of the antibodies (ranging from 0.25 to 10 ng/L) were then loaded into to the plate and incubated for 1 h. After washing the plates, SAHRP was loaded as

described above. Colour was developed with OPD substrate and the reaction was stopped with 4 mol/L H₂SO₄ as described above. Competition was recorded as positive when the absorbance decreased below 75% of that observed without unlabeled antibody.

PSA calibrators

Serial dilutions of four different PSA calibrators were used in the ELISAs for tPSA, fPSA or PSA- α_1 ACT complex. One calibrator was fPSA purified as indicated above, and its concentration was calculated from the absorption at 280 nm, using an extinction coefficient $\epsilon^{0.1\%}$ of 1.84. The second calibrator was partially purified PSA- α_1 ACT prepared as indicated above. The other two calibrator were obtained from the National Institute for Biological Standards and Control (NIBSC); one was the prostate-specific antigen (free) first international standard (NIBSC code 96/668), which consists of fPSA, and the other was the prostate-specific antigen (90:10) first international standard (NIBSC code 96/670) [PSA (90/10) Standard], which consists of a mixture of 90% PSA bound to α_1 ACT and 10% fPSA. To better compare the results, for PSA- α_1 ACT complex assay we only considered the 90% of PSA that is in the complexed form in the 90:10 first international standard, whereas for fPSA assay we only considered the 10% that is in the free form.

Supplementary Results

Characterization of monoclonal antibodies

Eight anti-PSA mAbs (M1, M15, M21, M29, M40, M50, M63, and M73) that gave a high signal in the screening test from two hybridoma fusions were selected. All of them were of the IgG₁ with kappa chain type and none exhibited cross-reactivity with female sera, assessed by incubation with different relative concentration of antibodies and PSA (see supplementary Figure S1), showing that female serum does not contain any component that competes with PSA for antibody binding.

The apparent dissociation constant (K_d) of each mAb for immobilized PSA or PSA in solution is shown in supplementary Table S1. The affinity of each antibody varied depending on whether PSA was or was not immobilized. The greatest affinity for immobilized PSA corresponded to M40 antibody (0.3×10^{-9} mol/L), whereas the M15 mAb showed the lowest affinity (178.4×10^{-9} mol/L). For PSA in solution, the M29 and M40 mAbs showed the highest affinity (8.9×10^{-9} mol/L and 10.1×10^{-9} mol/L, respectively) whereas the M15 gave the lowest affinity ($>200 \times 10^{-9}$ mol/L). As seen in supplementary Table S1, the K_d 's are more homogeneous for PSA in solution than for immobilized PSA. In general, all antibodies showed more affinity for immobilized PSA than for PSA in solution, except M50. This suggests that M50 recognizes an epitope that could be altered by slight conformational changes that may occur when PSA is bound to the ELISA plate.

SDS-PAGE and immunoblotting studies were performed to characterize the nature of the epitopes recognized by the mAbs (see supplementary Table S2). The results suggested that M1, M21, M29 and M73 mAbs detected linear epitopes on the PSA molecule that remained intact on the reduced forms of both fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT complex. In contrast, four mAbs, M15, M40, M50 and M63, seemed to recognize conformation-dependent epitopes on PSA- α_1 ACT complex that are lost under reducing conditions.

All pair combinations of the eight mAbs (excepting M15) were tested for reactivity with fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT in ELISAs. Some examples of sandwiching behaviour of the combinations are shown in supplementary Figure S3. We found that some pairs (all with M63) didn't detect PSA- α_1 ACT, for example, the M63/M50* and M63/M40* combinations seem to be specific for fPSA. Other pairs (M1/M21*, M21/M40*, M40/M50*, M40/M73* and M73/M50*) recognized fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT with the same efficiency, and could be used to measure tPSA. Only three combinations (M1/M40*, M1/M50* and M1/M73*) reacted a bit more efficiently with PSA- α_1 ACT than with fPSA. An * above indicates a biotinylated detecting antibody.

The eight mAbs were examined for the capacity to inhibit the binding of each labelled

counterpart to PSA. Supplementary Table S3 shows the results obtained. Competition was recorded when the absorbance decreased below 75% of that observed without unlabeled antibody. Results revealed two main clusters of epitopes, one recognized by M21, M29 and M63, and the other by M1, M15 and M40. The antibodies in each group seemed to recognize an identical epitope/s topographically closely related. The epitope for M73 did not appear to overlap with those of any of the other antibodies.

Supplementary Figure S2 shows the cross-reactivity with hK2 of the different anti-PSA mAbs. Only M73 significantly cross-reacted with purified hK2 in solution, compared to a specific anti-hK2 mAb.

Calibration and limit detection of the immunoassays for the PSA molecular forms

It is essential that methods for PSA are equimolar in their response to fPSA and PSA- α_1 ACT and calibrated to the International Standards to minimize the likelihood of clinical errors due to calibration issues⁸.

Supplementary Figure S4, top panel, shows calibration curves for the tPSA assay. Calibration curves of purified PSA diluted in blocking buffer were linear within the range of 0.3 to 10 μ g/L under the assay conditions used. No differences were seen when the dilutions of PSA were made in control plasma (data not shown). Serial dilutions of two reference PSA preparations obtained from the National Institute for Biological Standards and Control (NIBSC, UK) containing different proportion of free and complexed PSA gave similar responses than those obtained with purified PSA used in the assay. The detection limit of the assay, defined as the concentration of PSA that gave an absorbance equal to that of the assay buffer + 3 SD (calculated from 15 replicates), was 0.1 μ g/L of PSA. The intra- and interassay CVs for tPSA were 3-14% and 5-11%, respectively, at PSA concentrations of 0.22-2.6 μ g/L (n=10).

Supplementary Figure S4, central panel, shows calibration curves for the PSA- α_1 ACT assay. Calibration curves of partially purified PSA- α_1 ACT diluted in blocking buffer were linear within the range of 0.25 to 9 μ g/L under the assay conditions used. No differences were seen when

the dilutions of the complex were made in control plasma. Serial dilutions of PSA (90:10) Standard gave similar responses to those obtained with partially purified complex in the assay, whereas the PSA (free) Standard gave no signal in the assay up to a PSA concentration of 200 µg/L. To make clearer the comparison in the signals, only 90% of PSA that is in the complexed form in the PSA (90:10) Standard was considered. The detection limit of the assay, defined as the concentration of PSA complexed to α_1 ACT that gave an absorbance equal to that of the assay buffer + 3 SD (calculated from 15 replicates), was 0.05 µg/L of PSA. The intra- and interassay CVs were 2-7% and 6-9%, respectively, at PSA concentrations of 0.2-2.2 µg/L (n=10).

Supplementary Figure S4, lower panel, shows calibration curves for the fPSA assay. Calibration curves using the PSA (free) Standard diluted in blocking buffer were linear within the range of 0.05 to 2 µg/L under the assay conditions used. No differences were seen when the dilutions of PSA (free) Standard were made in control plasma. Serial dilutions of the PSA (90:10) Standard gave parallel responses to PSA (free) Standard in the assay. Again, only the 10% of PSA that is in the free form in the PSA (90:10) Standard was considered. The detection limit of the assay, defined as the concentration of PSA that gave an absorbance equal to that of the assay buffer + 3 SD (calculated from 15 replicates), was 0.04 µg/L PSA. The intra- and interassay CVs for tPSA were 4-11% and 5-15%, respectively, at PSA concentrations of 0.06-1.00 µg/L (n=10).

We used ROC curves to assess the clinical performance of the assays. Supplementary Tables S4, S5 and S6 show the sensitivity, specificity, and AUC of each assay in the 3 subgroups analyzed according to the tPSA. For the whole cohort of patients analyzed (tPSA between 0.76 and 975 µg/L), the FPR/CPR ratio (0.82) and the FPR (0.78) gave higher discrimination than tPSA (0.69) (supplementary Table S4). For the subgroup of patients with tPSA between ≥ 2.5 and < 4 µg/L, the FPR/CPR (0.77) and the FPR (0.76) again had the best discriminating potency compared to tPSA (0.53) (supplementary Table S5). For the tPSA range between ≥ 4 and < 10 µg/L, the FPR (0.81), CPR (0.79) and the FPR/CPR ratio gave better discrimination than tPSA (0.56) (supplementary Table S6). Finally, for the tPSA range between ≥ 10 and < 20 µg/L, all parameters analyzed showed better discrimination than tPSA (supplementary Table S7). In this range, using a cutoff point of 4.4 for the FPR/CPR ratio we would have avoided 30% biopsies without losing any

PCa patient.

Supplementary Figure S5 shows a decision curve analysis comparing the Standardized Net Benefit among our developed model (new model), total PSA values (PSA) and biopsy for all patients (All).

Supplementary Figure S6 shows the sensitivity and specificity profile plot for the predictive model.

Supplementary Figure S7 shows an effect plot depicting the relationship between tPSA and fPSA values and the probability of PCa.

We also estimated the improvement of our new predictive model versus the classical markers (tPSA levels) using the net reclassification improvement (NRI) and the integrated discrimination improvement (IDI) (Supplementary Table S8).

Supplementary Dataset (excel file) allows performing straightforward PCa predictions, according to our predictive model.

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Supplementary Tables & Figures

Supplementary Table S1. Apparent dissociation constants (K_d) of monoclonal anti-PSA antibodies for PSA.

mAb	Apparent K_d (nM)	
	(immobilized PSA)	(PSA in solution)
M1	26.0	154.7
M15	178.4	>200
M21	0.6	17.1
M29	4.2	8.9
M40	0.3	10.1
M50	112.9	27.7
M63	8.7	11.5
M73	2.4	12.9

Supplementary Table S2. Reactivity of anti-PSA monoclonal antibodies on immunoblots towards free PSA and PSA- α_1 ACT complex. *Linear and conformation-dependent epitope categories are based on antibody reactivity with free PSA and PSA- α_1 ACT complex in reducing and nonreducing SDS-polyacrylamide gels. +++, strong staining; ++, moderate staining; +, weak staining; -, no staining; F, antibody showed reactivity to intact PSA and several PSA fragments.

Antibody	Nonreducing SDS-PAGE		Reducing SDS-PAGE	
	free PSA	PSA- α_1 ACT	free PSA	PSA- α_1 ACT
<i>Linear epitopes*</i>				
<i>M1</i>	+++	+++	+++F	+++
<i>M21</i>	+++	+++	++	++
<i>M29</i>	+++	++	++	+
<i>M73</i>	+++	+++	++	++
<i>Conformational-dependent epitopes</i>				
<i>M15</i>	+	++	+	-
<i>M40</i>	+++	++	++	-
<i>M50</i>	+++	++	++F	-
<i>M63</i>	+++	+	+	-

Supplementary Table S3. Competition between unlabelled and labelled

monoclonal antibodies for binding to PSA. C, competition. N, no

competition. Left, unlabeled antibody. Top, labelled antibody.

	M21	M29	M63	M1	M15	M40	M50	M73
M21	C							
M29	C	C						
M63	C	C	C					
M1	N	N	N	C				
M15	N	N	N	C	C			
M40	N	C	N	C	C	C		
M50	N	N	N	N	N	C	C	
M73	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	C

Supplementary Table S4. Sensitivity (%), specificity (%), and AUC for total PSA, free PSA, PSA density, PSA- α_1 ACT, free-to-total PSA ratio (FPR), complexed-to-total PSA ratio (CPR) and FPR/CPR ratio for the 301 patients with PCa and 764 with benign biopsy, with tPSA between 0.76 and 975 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (whole cohort).^a CI, confidence interval; ^b $P < 0.001$ for the difference in AUC for: a) tPSA vs fPSA, tPSA vs PSA- α_1 ACT and tPSA vs FPR/CPR ratio; b) fPSA vs PSA- α_1 ACT, fPSA vs FPR, fPSA vs CPR and fPSA vs PSA- α_1 ACT; c) PSA- α_1 ACT vs CPR and PSA- α_1 ACT vs FPR/CPR ratio; d) FPR vs CPR and FPR vs FPR/CPR ratio; e) CPR vs FPR/CPR ratio.

Assay	Cut-off point	Sensitivity	Specificity	AUC (95% CI)*
Total PSA, $\mu\text{g/L}$	>0.78	100	0	0.69 (0.67-0.72) ^b
	>3.23	95	13	
	>4.15	90	20	
	>5.00	85	31	
PSA density	≤ 0.89	100	2.2	0.51 (0.43-0.58)
	≤ 0.56	95	7.2	
	≤ 0.49	90	9.4	
	≤ 0.33	85	18	
Free PSA, $\mu\text{g/L}$	≥ 0.08	100	0	0.54 (0.51-0.57)
	>0.39	95	4	
	>0.55	90	11	
	>0.63	85	14	
PSA- α_1 ACT, $\mu\text{g/L}$	>0.68	100	1	0.76 (0.73-0.79)
	>2.67	95	15	
	>3.60	90	34	
	>4.13	85	41	
FPR	≤ 71	100	1	0.78 (0.75-0.80)
	≤ 30	95	28	
	≤ 24	90	46	
	≤ 21	85	56	
CPR	>20	100	0	0.74 (0.64-0.81)
	>57	95	16	
	>61	90	24	
	>66	85	33	
FPR/CPR	≤ 23	100	5	0.82 (0.80-0.84)
	≤ 6.47	95	35	
	≤ 4.80	90	49	
	≤ 4.18	85	56	

Supplementary Table S5. Sensitivity (%), specificity (%), and AUC for total PSA, PSA density, free PSA, PSA- α_1 ACT, free-to-total PSA ratio (FPR), complexed-to-total PSA ratio (CPR) and FPR/CPR ratio for the 20 patients with PCa and 87 with benign biopsy, with tPSA between ≥ 2.5 and < 4 $\mu\text{g/L}$. ^a CI, confidence interval; ^b $P < 0.001$ for the difference in AUC for tPSA vs all other parameters. $P > 0.05$ for all other comparison.

Assay	Cut-off point	Sensitivity	Specificity	AUC (95% CI)*
Total PSA, $\mu\text{g/L}$	≥ 2.50	100	0	0.53 (0.44-0.63) ^b
	> 2.81	95	21	
	> 2.97	90	31	
	> 2.98	85	33	
PSA density	≤ 0.81	100	3	0.62 (0.34-0.85)
	≤ 0.62	95	7	
	≤ 0.53	90	11	
	≤ 0.47	85	15	
Free PSA, $\mu\text{g/L}$	≤ 0.91	100	25	0.74 (0.64-0.63)
	≤ 0.63	95	57	
	≤ 0.62	90	58	
	≤ 0.61	85	58	
PSA- α_1 ACT, $\mu\text{g/L}$	> 1.53	100	6	0.70 (0.60-0.78)
	> 1.98	95	18	
	> 2.16	90	31	
	> 2.26	85	33	
FPR	≤ 31	100	17	0.76 (0.66-0.83)
	≤ 28	95	22	
	≤ 21	90	54	
	≤ 18	85	61	
CPR	> 63	100	16	0.74 (0.64-0.81)
	> 67	95	18	
	> 79	90	49	
	> 81	85	50	
FPR/CPR	≤ 15	100	14	0.77 (0.68-0.85)
	≤ 13	95	35	
	≤ 4.80	90	49	
	≤ 4.18	85	56	

Supplementary Table S6. Sensitivity (%), specificity (%), and AUC for total PSA, free PSA, PSA density, PSA- α_1 ACT, free-to-total PSA ratio (FPR), complexed-to-total PSA ratio (CPR) and FPR/CPR ratio for the 126 patients with PCa and 464 with benign biopsy, with tPSA between ≥ 4 and < 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$. ^a CI, confidence interval; ^b $P < 0.001$ for the difference in AUC for total PSA vs all other parameters. $P > 0.05$ for all other comparison.

Assay	Cut-off point	Sensitivity	Specificity	AUC (95% CI)
Total PSA, $\mu\text{g/L}$	> 4.04	100	1	0.56 (0.53-0.61) ^b
	> 4.20	95	6	
	> 4.60	90	14	
	> 4.90	85	21	
PSA density	≤ 0.78	100	2	0.52 (0.43-0.61)
	≤ 0.55	95	5	
	≤ 0.49	90	8	
	≤ 0.41	85	14	
Free PSA, $\mu\text{g/L}$	≤ 3.43	100	3	0.73 (0.68-0.76)
	≤ 2.01	95	25	
	≤ 1.52	90	45	
	≤ 1.42	85	49	
PSA- α_1 ACT, $\mu\text{g/L}$	> 2.25	100	2	0.71 (0.67-0.74)
	> 3.36	95	18	
	> 3.96	90	34	
	> 4.05	85	36	
FPR	≤ 53	100	1	0.81 (0.78-0.84)
	≤ 27	95	37	
	≤ 23	90	46	
	≤ 19	85	61	
CPR	> 44	100	3	0.79 (0.75-0.82)
	> 69	95	35	
	> 72	90	43	
	> 79	85	60	
FPR/CPR	≤ 23	100	1	0.79 (0.76-0.82)
	≤ 6	95	35	
	≤ 5	90	50	
	≤ 4	85	55	

Supplementary Table S7. Sensitivity (%), specificity (%), and AUC for total PSA, PSA density, free PSA, PSA- α_1 ACT, free-to-total PSA ratio (FPR), complexed-to-total PSA ratio (CPR) and FPR/CPR ratio for the 66 patients with PCa and 130 with benign biopsy, with tPSA between ≥ 10 and < 20 $\mu\text{g/L}$. ^a CI, confidence interval; ^b $P < 0.001$ for the difference in AUC for total PSA vs all other parameters. $P > 0.05$ for all other comparison.

Assay	Cut point	Sensitivity	Specificity	AUC(95% CI) ^a
Total PSA, $\mu\text{g/L}$	>10.12	100	4	0.55 (0.48-0.62) ^b
	>10.20	95	5	
	>10.76	90	15	
	>11.00	85	19	
PSA density	≤ 0.27	100	8	0.62 (0.34-0.85)
	≤ 0.25	95	16	
	≤ 0.22	90	21	
	≤ 0.18	85	25	
Free PSA, $\mu\text{g/L}$	≤ 6.71	100	6	0.78 (0.71-0.84)
	≤ 3.33	95	25	
	≤ 3.14	90	50	
	≤ 2.90	85	56	
PSA- α_1 ACT, $\mu\text{g/L}$	>6.68	100	18	0.77 (0.70-0.82)
	>3.36	95	38	
	>3.96	90	44	
	>4.05	85	56	
FPR	≤ 38	100	19	0.80 (0.74-0.86)
	≤ 30	95	33	
	≤ 23	90	59	
	≤ 20	85	65	
CPR	>44	100	3	0.79 (0.75-0.82)
	>69	95	35	
	>72	90	43	
	>79	85	60	
FPR/CPR	≤ 4.4	100	30	0.78 (0.64-0.89)
	≤ 4.3	95	31	
	≤ 4.2	90	32	
	≤ 2.6	85	67	

Supplementary Table S8. Net Reclassification Improvement (NRI) and Integrated Discrimination Improvement (IDI) to determine the improvement of the new predictive model (multivariable logistic regression model) *versus* total PSA levels to estimate the risk of PCa. *Benign biopsy.

Predictive model <i>vs</i> PSA (95% CI)	
NRI	0.870 (0.725-1.015)
NRI for PCa	0.374 (0.250-0.498)
NRI for BB*	0.496 (0.422-0.571)
IDI	0.201 (0.171-0.232)
Increase for PCa (sensitivity)	0.142
Decrease for BB (specificity)	0.059

Supplementary Figure S1. Serum competition with purified PSA for the eight immobilized monoclonal anti-PSA antibody binding. Serum from women (+) or buffer (-) was diluted to 50% with 0.137 mol/L NaCl, 2.7 mmol/L KCl, pH 7.4 and incubated in microtiter plates coated with 0.5 or 5.0 mg/L anti-PSA mAb and then with 0.18 mg/L PSA (wells with 0.5 mg/L mAb) or either 0.09 mg/L or 0.5 mg/L PSA (wells with 5 mg/L mAb), as indicated in Methods. (A) 0.5 mg/L mAb and 0.18 mg/L PSA. (B) 5 mg/L mAb and 0.09 mg/L PSA. (C) 5 mg/L mAb and 0.5 mg/L PSA.

Supplementary Figure S2. Cross-reactivity of monoclonal anti-PSA antibodies with purified hK2. ELISA plates coated with the corresponding mAb were incubated with 20 $\mu\text{g/L}$ hK2 or 20 $\mu\text{g/L}$ PSA. For comparison, a specific anti-hK2 mAb was also analyzed. hK2 or PSA bound was detected with polyclonal anti-PSA labelled with HRP.

Supplementary Figure S3. Reactivity of several pairs of anti-PSA mAbs towards free PSA and PSA: α_1 ACT. ELISA plates, coated with the indicated unlabeled antibody, were incubated with free PSA (●) or PSA: α_1 ACT complex (▲) at different concentrations as indicated. PSA bound was detected with the corresponding labelled (*) antibody. PSA: α_1 ACT is expressed as $\mu\text{g/L}$ of PSA in complex with α_1 ACT.

Supplementary Figure S4. Calibration curves for total PSA, PSA- α_1 ACT complex, and free PSA immunoassays. For PSA- α_1 ACT, PSA is expressed as $\mu\text{g/L}$ of PSA in complex with α_1 ACT. The following capture and detecting mAb were used: For total PSA, M40 and M73*; for PSA- α_1 ACT complex, M40 and rabbit anti-human α_1 ACT*; for free PSA, M63 and M50*, respectively. The asterisk indicates labelled antibody.

Supplementary Figure S5. Decision curve analysis comparing the Standardized Net Benefit among our developed model (new model), total PSA values (PSA) and biopsy for all patients (All).

Supplementary Figure 6. Sensitivity and specificity profile plot for the predictive model.

Supplementary Figure S7. Effects plot depicting the relationship between total PSA (tPSA) and free PSA (fPSA) values and the probability of cancer. Red values represent higher PCa probabilities and blue values represent lower PCa probabilities.

